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BACTERIAL COMPLICATIONS OF VARICELLA IN UNVACCINATED CHILDREN

Abstract.

The article summarises current data on the epidemiology, pathogenesis and clinical spectrum of bacterial complications of chickenpox in unvaccinated children, as well as the preventive role of vaccination.

Keywords: varicella, bacterial complications, unvaccinated children, secondary infection, vaccination.

Varicella, caused by the Varicella-Zoster virus (VZV), is a highly contagious airborne infection that predominantly affects children. [1]. Before the development vaccine, the disease was nearly usual in childhood, particularly among preschoolaged children in regions without widespread immunization. Although varicella is generally regarded as a benign and self-limiting illness, it remains globally endemic, with periodic outbreaks occurring in populations sufficient to sustain continuous transmission. Importantly, varicella may lead to severe complications requiring hospitalization, especially in unvaccinated children. Secondary bacterial infections represent the principal cause of varicella-related morbidity and mortality. The risk of such complications is further increased in children with chronic underlying diseases, immunological immaturity, or compromised skin integrity during the vesicular stage of the disease. [2,3,4].

Epidemiology of bacterial Complications. The incidence of bacterial complications in children with varicella is estimated at 2–6%, with substantially higher rates reported in unvaccinated populations [5]. Skin and soft tissue infections are the most frequent complications, followed by invasive bacterial diseases. Epidemiological data consistently demonstrate a significant reduction in complication rates in regions with high vaccination coverage. The most commonly isolated pathogens are *Streptococcus pyogenes* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Invasive group A streptococcal infections, although rare, are associated with high morbidity and mortality [6].

Pathogenesis. The pathogenesis of bacterial complications in varicella is multifactorial. Vesicular skin lesions disrupt the epidermal barrier, facilitating bacterial entry. Intense pruritus and scratching further increase the risk of secondary infection. Additionally, VZV induces transient immunosuppression by impairing cell-mediated immunity, reducing T-lymphocyte function, and modulating innate immune responses. These mechanisms collectively predispose infected children to bacterial superinfection, particularly during the acute phase of illness [6, 7].

Clinical spectrum of bacterial complications.

Skin and soft tissue Infections like impetigo, cellulitis, toxicoderma and erysipelas are the most common bacterial complications are associated with Varicella Zoster Virus. Severe forms include necrotizing fasciitis, which progresses rapidly and requires urgent surgical and antimicrobial intervention. The clinical manifestation of these complications include local and general pattern. Local symptoms consist of redness in the affected area, a significant increase in tissue volume due to swelling, intense, throbbing pain that worsens with touch or movement, the presence of purulent secretions from the affected area, compaction or softening of tissues at the site of the lesion, local hyperthermia. [8, 9, 10]. VZV infection can cause a number of serious invasive bacterial disease in unvaccinated children: sepsis, bacteremia, meningitis, and streptococcal toxic shock syndrome. These conditions are associated with prolonged hospitalization and increased risk of fatal outcomes [10].

Impact of Vaccination. Herpes zoster is a disease that can be prevented with a vaccine. Varicella vaccination has demonstrated high effectiveness in reducing disease incidence and severity. Numerous studies report a $\geq 80\%$ reduction in varicella-related hospitalizations and bacterial complications following the implementation of routine immunization programs [11, 12]. Breakthrough varicella in vaccinated children is typically mild and rarely complicated by secondary bacterial infections, underscoring the protective effect of vaccination beyond disease prevention. [13]

Conclusions. Bacterial complications remain the most serious consequence of varicella in unvaccinated children. Disruption of the skin barrier and virus-induced immunosuppression are central to their development. Skin and soft tissue infections are the most frequent complications, while invasive bacterial diseases, although uncommon, carry a high risk of severe outcomes. Widespread varicella vaccination is the most effective strategy for preventing primary infection and associated bacterial complications. Countries where varicella is an important public health burden could consider introducing varicella vaccination in the routine childhood immunization programme.

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